

Supplementary Material for Slicing with Guaranteed Quality of Service in WiFi Networks

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Abstract—In this document we present in detail all the theoretical results and demonstrations which show the performance characteristics of the proposed slicing solution.

Index Terms—5G, Quality of service, Stochastic optimization, Wireless LAN, Wireless network slicing, Resource management.

S.I. PROOF OF BOUNDED DELAY

Hereafter we provide a simple and intuitive proof, which shows that any algorithm that ensures that $Q_{n,s}(t) \leq Q_{n,s}^{max} \forall t \geq 0$ and $Z_{n,s}(t) \leq Z_{n,s}^{max} \forall t \geq 0$ guarantees that packet delay is bounded. Even more, the bound is given by $W_{n,s}^{max} = \left\lceil \frac{Q_{n,s}^{max} + Z_{n,s}^{max}}{\epsilon_{n,s}} \right\rceil$.

Proof. Let us observe that the worst case in possible delays for a packet appears when it arrives to an almost full $Q_{n,s}$ queue. Let us assume that packet p arrives at time t , that no packet is dropped or transmitted on that time slot, and that the arrival of p makes the queue full: $Q_{n,s}(t+1) = Q_{n,s}^{max}$. Therefore, packet p needs to wait until all previous packets are transmitted or dropped to leave the queue. It is easy to see that the worst case on delay for packet p is that in the following time slots, no packet is transmitted neither dropped from the queue.

On the other hand, we have the virtual queue $Z_{n,s}(t+1) = [Z_{n,s}(t) + \epsilon_{n,s} - R_{n,s}(t) - D_{n,s}(t)]^+$. In this queue, new traffic is always arriving at a rate of $\epsilon_{n,s}$ packets per slot. Therefore, when this queue is full, it enforces that a packet is transmitted or dropped. Let us assume the worst case for packet p , which is that $Z_{n,s}(t) = 0$. In this case, given that the queue gets data at a rate of $\epsilon_{n,s}$ and that the queue is bounded by $Z_{n,s}^{max}$, it will take $T_1 = \frac{Z_{n,s}^{max}}{\epsilon_{n,s}}$ to get full.

Hence, after time slot T_1 , packets are transmitted or dropped at least by a rate of $\epsilon_{n,s}$ per slot to maintain the queue equal or below its bound. Therefore, it will take $T_2 = \frac{Q_{n,s}^{max}}{\epsilon_{n,s}}$ time slots for the packet p to be at the head of the queue. Then, the worst possible delay for any packet is given by

$$W_{n,s}^{max} = T_1 + T_2 = \frac{Q_{n,s}^{max} + Z_{n,s}^{max}}{\epsilon_{n,s}}$$

□

S.II. ANALYSIS AND DEMONSTRATIONS FOR THE PROPOSED SOLUTION

The objective of this section is to demonstrate that the proposed mechanism of minimizing the right-hand side of

Equation (32) finds an approximate solution to the problem in (10)-(18) which utility is close to the optimal utility, all the queues are stabilized and all the constraints and delay bounds are satisfied. The following proofs are based on the proofs provided by M. Neely in [SI], however, we present them here with the purpose of better understanding the solution performance and because our approach differs in some particularities with the original work of Neely.

For the following demonstrations some assumptions we mentioned in the main article are needed as well as some bounds on the system parameters. Let us first review some of the bounds we have defined and are satisfied by our solution:

$$\begin{aligned} A_{n,s}(t) &\leq A_{n,s}^{max} \quad \forall s \in \mathcal{S}, \forall n \in \mathcal{N}_s, \forall t \\ R_{n,s}(t) &\leq R_{n,s}^{max} \quad \forall s \in \mathcal{S}, \forall n \in \mathcal{N}_s, \forall t \\ D_{n,s}(t) &\leq D_{n,s}^{max} = A_{n,s}^{max} \quad \forall s \in \mathcal{S}, \forall n \in \mathcal{N}_s, \forall t \\ X_s(t) &\leq 1 \quad \forall s \in \mathcal{S}, \forall n \in \mathcal{N}_s, \forall t \\ \gamma_{n,s}(t) &\leq \gamma_{n,s}^{max} = A_{n,s}^{max} \quad \forall s \in \mathcal{S}, \forall n \in \mathcal{N}_s, \forall t \\ \phi(\gamma(t)) &\leq \phi^{max} = \log(\gamma_{1_1}^{max}, \dots, \gamma_{n,s}^{max}) \quad \forall t \end{aligned} \quad (S1)$$

Let us also summarize the necessary assumptions:

Assumption 1. Let us consider $\omega(t) = [A(t), C(t)]$ as the network state consisting of the arrivals $A_{n,s}(t)$ and the channel capacities $C_{n,s}(t)$ at each client. We assume $\omega(t)$ is an stochastic process which is i.i.d. over slots and is stationary with distribution probability $\pi(\omega)$.

Assumption 2. The problems defined in (10)-(18) and in (21)-(24) are feasible. In other words, for any vector of possible arrival rates there exists an allocation of transmission airtime ratios which solves the problem.

Assumption 3. All the real and virtual queues are initially empty.

Assumptions 1 and 3 are needed for a clear theoretical demonstration. However, in [SI] it is shown that the drift-plus-penalty method also works in scenarios where the channel is modeled as a Markovian process. Even more, Assumption 3 is used in this thesis to simplify the demonstration, however, similar results are obtained without the Assumption.

A. Delay Bounds

At first, we will demonstrate that the proposed algorithm guarantees that there exists a bound on both $Q_{n,s}(t)$ and $Z_{n,s}(t)$ queues. Therefore, we propose the following theorem.

Theorem 1. Assuming the arrivals and drops are bounded by $A_{n,s}^{max}$ and that $\epsilon_{n,s} \leq A_{n,s}^{max}$, then the proposed algorithm ensures that:

$$Q_{n,s}(t) \leq Q_{n,s}^{max}, Z_{n,s}(t) \leq Z_{n,s}^{max}, Y_{n,s}(t) \leq Y_{n,s}^{max} \forall t \quad (S2)$$

where:

$$\begin{aligned} Q_{n,s}^{max} &= V\omega + 2A_{n,s}^{max} \\ Z_{n,s}^{max} &= V\omega + A_{n,s}^{max} + \epsilon_{n,s} \\ Y_{n,s}^{max} &= V\omega + A_{n,s}^{max} \end{aligned} \quad (S3)$$

Proof. Let us first observe that the virtual queue $Y_{n,s}(t)$ is bounded. From the result (35) which defines the optimal auxiliary variables and the bound $\gamma_{n,s}(t) \geq 0$ it is easy to ascertain that when $Y_{n,s}(t) \geq V\omega$, the algorithm will choose $\gamma_{n,s}(t) = 0$. Then, the virtual queue defined in (28) will not grow in time slot $t+1$. On the other hand, when $Y_{n,s}(t) < V\omega$ the virtual queue will follow the dynamics defined in (28) and given that $\gamma_{n,s}(t) \leq A_{n,s}^{max}$, it can increase at most by $A_{n,s}^{max}$. Therefore, we have an upper bound of the virtual queue, given by $Y_{n,s}^{max} = V\omega + A_{n,s}^{max}$.

Next, we demonstrate that there exist constants $Q_{n,s}^{max}$ and $Z_{n,s}^{max}$ which are respectively upper bounds for $Q_{n,s}(t)$ (as defined in (4)) and $Z_{n,s}(t)$ (as defined in (5)). As mentioned, for this proof we assume that $0 \leq \epsilon_{n,s} \leq D_{n,s}^{max}$ and $D_{n,s}^{max} = A_{n,s}^{max}$ for all clients and slices.

It is easy to see from the dropping decision (38) that when $Q_{n,s}(t) > Y_{n,s}^{max}$, the mechanism will drop $A_{n,s}^{max}$ packets from the queue. Therefore, as the maximum arrival rate in one slot is given by $A_{n,s}^{max}$, the queue will not grow at the next slot. On the other case, when $Q_{n,s}(t) \leq Y_{n,s}^{max}$, the queue will grow at maximum by $A_{n,s}^{max}$, such that $Q_{n,s}(t+1) \leq Y_{n,s}^{max} + A_{n,s}^{max} \forall t$. Hence, we can conclude that $Q_{n,s}(t) \leq Y_{n,s}^{max} + A_{n,s}^{max} \forall t$.

For $Z_{n,s}(t)$ the proof is very similar. If $Z_{n,s}(t) > Y_{n,s}^{max}$, then the decision is to drop $D_{n,s}^{max}$ packets from the queue. As $0 \leq \epsilon_{n,s} \leq D_{n,s}^{max}$, the queue cannot grow at the next slot. If $Z_{n,s}(t) \leq Y_{n,s}^{max}$, then $Z_{n,s}(t+1) \leq Y_{n,s}^{max} + \epsilon_{n,s}$. \square

As we know from Section S.I, the delay bound is given by $W_{n,s}^{max} = \left\lceil \frac{Q_{n,s}^{max} + Z_{n,s}^{max}}{\epsilon_{n,s}} \right\rceil$ then, substituting we have:

$$W_{n,s}^{max} = \left\lceil \frac{2V\omega + 3A_{n,s}^{max} + \epsilon_{n,s}}{\epsilon_{n,s}} \right\rceil \quad (S4)$$

Therefore, we have obtained an upper bound on the queuing delay of each client which depends on a set of configuration parameters of the solution (V , ω and $\epsilon_{n,s}$) and on an upper bound of the traffic arrival rate. This result is important as it can be used to adjust the scheduler parameters to a given delay bound requirement.

B. Optimal Utility

Hereafter, we demonstrate that the algorithm proposed in the main article achieves an utility which approximates the optimal utility by a factor depending on V .

Theorem 2. Supposing that Assumptions (1)-(3) hold. If the proposed algorithm is implemented with a constant $V > 0$,

then all queues are mean rate stable and the obtained utility satisfies:

$$\phi(\bar{\mathbf{u}}) \geq \phi^{opt} - \frac{B}{V} \quad (S5)$$

where ϕ^{opt} is the maximum utility of the problem (10)-(18).

Before presenting the proofs, we will introduce the definition of a special kind of control policies. Let us consider a particular type of control policy that solves the problem in (10)-(18) and which does not consider the queue backlog on the decisions. These type of policies are called ω -only policies, as they observe the network state $\omega(t)$ at each slot t and independently choose a control action $x(t)$ as a function only of the observed $\omega(t)$. The following demonstrations are based on an important result (which demonstration exceeds the scope of this document) from [S1] which shows that the optimal utility and the constraints satisfaction of our stochastic optimization problem can be achieved by ω -only policies.

Proof. Hereafter we demonstrate the utility bound from the previous Theorem. Because the proposed drift-plus-penalty algorithm minimizes a bound on (31) on every slot, we have that it is less or equal than the bound obtained by any other policy and any vector γ . In particular we have that:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta(\Theta(t)) - V\mathbb{E}\{\phi(\gamma(t)) \mid \Theta(t)\} &\leq B - V\phi(\gamma^*) \\ &+ \sum_{s \in \mathcal{S}} \sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}_s} G_{n,s}(t) \mathbb{E}\{-R_{n,s}^*(t) + K_s \mid \Theta(t)\} \\ &+ \sum_{s \in \mathcal{S}} \sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}_s} Q_{n,s}(t) \mathbb{E}\{A_{n,s}(t) - R_{n,s}^*(t) - D_{n,s}^*(t) \mid \Theta(t)\} \\ &+ \sum_{s \in \mathcal{S}} \sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}_s} Z_{n,s}(t) \mathbb{E}\{\epsilon_{n,s} - R_{n,s}^*(t) - D_{n,s}^*(t) \mid \Theta(t)\} \\ &+ \sum_{s \in \mathcal{S}} \sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}_s} Y_{n,s}(t) \mathbb{E}\{\gamma_{n,s}^*(t) - A_{n,s}(t) + D_{n,s}^*(t) \mid \Theta(t)\} \\ &+ \sum_{s=1}^S U_s(t) \mathbb{E}\{X_s^*(t) - H_s \mid \Theta(t)\} \end{aligned} \quad (S6)$$

where γ^* is any feasible vector, where $x^*(t)$, $D^*(t)$ are the decisions of any other alternative policy and where $R^*(t)$, $X^*(t)$ are the resulting attribute values of the system under those decisions.

Now let us consider that $x^*(t)$ are the decisions taken by the ω -only policy which yields the optimal utility and satisfies all the constraints of our problem. Considering that this is a ω -only policy and that from Assumption 1 we know that $\omega(t)$ is i.i.d., the values of $R^*(t)$, $D^*(t)$, $X^*(t)$ are independent of the queue backlogs $\Theta(t)$. Hence, for example $\mathbb{E}\{-R_{n,s}^*(t) + K_s \mid \Theta(t)\} = \mathbb{E}\{-R_{n,s}^*(t) + K_s\}$ where this new expectations are with respect to the network state $\omega(t)$ and the actions $x(t)$. Given that this policy obtains optimal utility and satisfies all constraints (it maintains all queues mean rate stable), it is true that:

$$\begin{aligned} \phi(\gamma^*) &= \phi^{opt} \\ \mathbb{E}\{-R_{n,s}^*(t)\} &\leq -K_s \\ \mathbb{E}\{A_{n,s}(t)\} &\leq \mathbb{E}\{R_{n,s}^*(t) + D_{n,s}^*(t)\} \\ \epsilon_{n,s} &\leq \mathbb{E}\{R_{n,s}^*(t) + D_{n,s}^*(t)\} \\ \gamma_{n,s}^*(t) &\leq \mathbb{E}\{A_{n,s}(t) - D_{n,s}^*(t)\} \end{aligned} \quad (S7)$$

Therefore, using the i.i.d. condition of $\omega(t)$ and substituting the previous result in (S6) yields:

$$\Delta(\Theta(t)) - V\mathbb{E}\{\phi(\gamma(t)) \mid \Theta(t)\} \leq B - V\phi^{opt} \quad (\text{S8})$$

Let us consider the previous equation for any time $\tau \leq 0$. Taking expectation on both sides and using the definition of the Lyapunov drift we obtain¹:

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathbb{E}\{\mathbb{E}\{L(\Theta(\tau+1)) - L(\Theta(\tau)) \mid \Theta(\tau)\}\} - \\ & V\mathbb{E}\{\mathbb{E}\{\phi(\gamma(\tau)) \mid \Theta(\tau)\}\} \leq B - V\phi^{opt} \end{aligned} \quad (\text{S9})$$

Using the *law of iterated expectations* we have:

$$\mathbb{E}\{L(\Theta(\tau+1))\} - \mathbb{E}\{L(\Theta(\tau))\} - V\mathbb{E}\{\phi(\gamma(\tau))\} \leq B - V\phi^{opt} \quad (\text{S10})$$

Summing the above over $\tau \in \{0, 1, \dots, t-1\}$ for some $t > 0$ and using the law of telescoping sums yields:

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathbb{E}\{L(\Theta(t))\} - \mathbb{E}\{L(\Theta(0))\} - V \sum_{\tau=0}^{t-1} \mathbb{E}\{\phi(\gamma(\tau))\} \\ & \leq Bt - Vt\phi^{opt} \end{aligned} \quad (\text{S11})$$

Rearranging terms, using the fact that $\mathbb{E}\{L(\Theta(t))\} \geq 0$ and dividing by Vt we get:

$$\frac{1}{t} \sum_{\tau=0}^{t-1} \mathbb{E}\{\phi(\gamma(\tau))\} \geq \phi^{opt} - \frac{B}{V} - \frac{\mathbb{E}\{L(\Theta(0))\}}{Vt} \quad (\text{S12})$$

By definition we know that $\phi(\gamma(t))$ is a concave function, then by Jensen's inequality we know that $\frac{1}{t} \sum_{\tau=0}^{t-1} \mathbb{E}\{\phi(\gamma(\tau))\} \leq \phi(\frac{1}{t} \sum_{\tau=0}^{t-1} \mathbb{E}\{\gamma(\tau)\})$, hence we have:

$$\phi(\bar{\gamma}(t)) \geq \phi^{opt} - \frac{B}{V} - \frac{\mathbb{E}\{L(\Theta(0))\}}{Vt} \quad (\text{S13})$$

where $\bar{\gamma}(t) = \frac{1}{t} \sum_{\tau=0}^{t-1} \mathbb{E}\{\gamma(\tau)\}$. Taking limits yields:

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \phi(\bar{\gamma}(t)) \geq \phi^{opt} - \frac{B}{V} \quad (\text{S14})$$

On the other hand, from the definition of the queue dynamics (28) it is easy to observe that for any slot $\tau \geq 0$:

$$\begin{aligned} & Y_{n,s}(\tau+1) \geq Y_{n,s}(\tau) + \gamma_{n,s}(\tau) - u_{n,s}(\tau) \\ & Y_{n,s}(\tau+1) - Y_{n,s}(\tau) \geq \gamma_{n,s}(\tau) - u_{n,s}(\tau) \end{aligned} \quad (\text{S15})$$

Summing the above equations over $\tau \in \{0, \dots, t-1\}$ and using the law of telescoping sums we obtain:

$$Y_{n,s}(t) - Y_{n,s}(0) \geq \sum_{\tau=0}^{t-1} \gamma_{n,s}(\tau) - \sum_{\tau=0}^{t-1} u_{n,s}(\tau) \quad (\text{S16})$$

Then, dividing all by t yields:

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{Y_{n,s}(t)}{t} - \frac{Y_{n,s}(0)}{t} \geq \frac{1}{t} \sum_{\tau=0}^{t-1} \gamma_{n,s}(\tau) - \frac{1}{t} \sum_{\tau=0}^{t-1} u_{n,s}(\tau) \\ & \frac{Y_{n,s}(t)}{t} - \frac{Y_{n,s}(0)}{t} \geq \bar{\gamma}_{n,s}(t) - \bar{u}_{n,s}(t) \\ & \bar{u}_{n,s}(t) \geq \bar{\gamma}_{n,s}(t) - \frac{Y_{n,s}(t)}{t} + \frac{Y_{n,s}(0)}{t} \end{aligned} \quad (\text{S17})$$

¹Note that all the values on the right-hand-side are constants.

Taking limits and using the previous result of $Y_{n,s}(t) \leq Y_{n,s}^{max} \forall t$ we have:

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \bar{u}_{n,s}(t) \geq \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \bar{\gamma}_{n,s}(t) \quad (\text{S18})$$

Therefore, given that $\phi(\mathbf{u})$ is continuous and non-decreasing, we can show that:

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \phi(\bar{\mathbf{u}}(t)) \geq \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \phi(\bar{\boldsymbol{\gamma}}(t)) \quad (\text{S19})$$

Finally, using this in (S14) we get:

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \phi(\bar{\mathbf{u}}(t)) \geq \phi^{opt} - \frac{B}{V} \quad (\text{S20})$$

which proves the theorem. \square

C. Constraint Satisfaction

The objective of this part is to show that the constraints of the initial problem in (10)-(18) are satisfied by the proposed algorithm and that the queue backlogs are bounded. For this we will use the following definition for queue stability:

Definition 1. Let us consider a queue with queue backlog defined by a discrete time process $Q(t)$. We say the queue is *mean rate stable* if:

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\mathbb{E}\{|Q(t)|\}}{t} = 0 \quad (\text{S21})$$

Proof. Constraints (15)-(18) are satisfied straightforward by the scheduling algorithm implementation. From the delay bound analysis in Section S.II.A we have found that the queues $Q_{n,s}(t)$ and $Z_{n,s}(t)$ are bounded for all t . Therefore it is easy to show that this queues are stable as requested by constraints (14) and (15), but even more, they are mean rate stable.

It is remaining to show that constraints (11) and (12) are also satisfied. For this, we will show that the virtual queues associated to these constraints are mean rate stable and then, that mean rate stability of implies the satisfaction of the constraints.

Let us assume that the expected reward is upper bounded by a given finite value ϕ^{max} . Therefore, for all time slots t and all possible control policies it satisfies:

$$\mathbb{E}\{\phi(t)\} \leq \phi^{max} \quad (\text{S22})$$

Using the previous assumption and rearranging the terms of (S11) we obtain:

$$\mathbb{E}\{L(\Theta(t))\} \leq \mathbb{E}\{L(\Theta(0))\} + (B - V(\phi^{opt} + \phi^{max}))t \quad (\text{S23})$$

Let us consider we have N queues (virtual and real) in total and use $\Theta_n(t)$ to note any of the queues of the system. Using the definition of $L(\Theta(t))$ we obtain:

$$\frac{1}{2} \sum_{n=1}^N \mathbb{E}\{\Theta_n(t)^2\} \leq \mathbb{E}\{L(\Theta(0))\} + (B - V(\phi^{opt} + \phi^{max}))t \quad (\text{S24})$$

Then, for each queue n we also have:

$$\mathbb{E}\{\Theta_n(t)^2\} \leq 2\mathbb{E}\{L(\Theta(0))\} + 2(B - V(\phi^{opt} + \phi^{max}))t \quad (\text{S25})$$

Given that $\Theta_n(t)^2 = |\Theta_n(t)|^2$ and that $\mathbb{E}\{|\Theta_n(t)|^2\} \geq \mathbb{E}\{|\Theta_n(t)|\}^2$:

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathbb{E}\{|\Theta_n(t)|\} \\ & \leq \sqrt{2\mathbb{E}\{L(\Theta(0))\} + 2(B - V(\phi^{opt} + \phi^{max}))t} \end{aligned} \quad (\text{S26})$$

Dividing by t and taking limits we obtain:

$$\begin{aligned} & \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\mathbb{E}\{|\Theta_n(t)|\}}{t} \\ & \leq \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \sqrt{\frac{2\mathbb{E}\{L(\Theta(0))\}}{t^2} + \frac{2(B - V(\phi^{opt} + \phi^{max}))}{t}} = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (\text{S27})$$

Then, we have shown that all queues $\Theta(t) = [Q(t), Z(t), G(t), U(t), Y(t)]$ are mean rate stable. \square

Now let us show that mean rate stability of the virtual queues implies the satisfaction of the initial constraints. Let us consider the virtual queue $G_{n,s}(t)$ update equations associated to constraint (11):

$$G_{n,s}(t+1) = [G_{n,s}(t) - R_{n,s}(t) + K_s]^+ \quad (\text{S28})$$

Then, it is easy to show that, for any $\tau \geq 0$:

$$G_{n,s}(\tau+1) - G_{n,s}(\tau) \geq -R_{n,s}(\tau) + K_s \quad (\text{S29})$$

Summing the above equation over $\tau \in \{0, \dots, t-1\}$, using the law of telescoping sums and dividing by t yields:

$$\frac{G_{n,s}(t)}{t} - \frac{G_{n,s}(0)}{t} \geq \frac{1}{t} \sum_{\tau=0}^{t-1} -R_{n,s}(\tau) + K_s \quad (\text{S30})$$

Taking expectations and taking the limit $t \rightarrow \infty$ over the previous equations shows:

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\mathbb{E}\{G_{n,s}(t)\}}{t} \geq \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{t} \sum_{\tau=0}^{t-1} \mathbb{E}\{-R_{n,s}(\tau)\} + K_s \quad (\text{S31})$$

From the previous analysis we know that the virtual queues $G_{n,s}(t)$ are mean rate stable. Then, from the definition of mean rate stability we know that the left-hand side of the previous equation is 0, therefore:

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{t} \sum_{\tau=0}^{t-1} \mathbb{E}\{R_{n,s}(\tau)\} \geq K_s \quad (\text{S32})$$

which is the initial constraint (11).

The exact same reasoning can be applied to virtual queue $U_{n,s}(t)$ associated to constraint (12).

REFERENCES

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